

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR IN COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT (CAI) TESTS OF CF/PEEK(APC-2) AND CONVENTIONAL CF/EPOXY FLAT LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Compression after impact (CAI) tests are conducted for quasi-isotropic thick plates with 48 plies of NASA method and for plates with 32 plies of SACMA method. Specimens are made of CF/PEEK(APC-2) and conventional CF/Epoxy for NASA plates and CF/Epoxy for SACMA plates. In NASA CAI tests sequence of delamination buckling and its propagation is well revealed by various experimental techniques. One unique technique here is the other is thermo-mechanical stress analysis using high accuracy infrared sensor. An arresting of delamination propagation just before catastrophic failure due to high fracture toughness is well captured first. Initial buckling properties of delaminated region by impact are extensively discussed next. Numerical predictions of initial buckling stress based on modelled geometry of the delaminated region simplified from its precise structure agree fairly with the experimental results. In-plane stress distribution in the delaminated region before initial buckling is measured by an thermo-mechanical system and compared also favorably with finite element predictions.

INTRODUCTION

Compression after impact (CAI) characteristics eventually govern practical strength design of composite primary structures of modern aircraft. Moreover, CAI values of carbon fiber (CF) / polymer composites are rated as one of the major material screening parameters. Therefore, two types of testing procedures, NASA¹ and SACMA² methods, are proposed as standards, and enormous CAI data are accumulated. Now, these data themselves are very common material characteristics. However, detailed experimental examinations of CAI tests of carbon fiber/polymeric material composites (CFRP) are not extensively performed so far. Sequence of mechanical behavior occurring during the tests and hidden mechanisms are still somewhat unknown to composite researchers.

In order to clarify such mechanical phenomena, detailed CAI experiments are conducted for conventional CF/Epoxy and CF/PEEK (APC-2) composite systems. Initial buckling and delamination propagation are the most focussed point of interest. The second purpose is to understand the difference in behavior between two polymeric composite systems. A Moire-

topography camera, a ultrasonic C-scanner, and a thermo-mechanical stress analyzer system using high-accuracy infrared sensor are used here as key experimental devices. Concerning initial buckling prediction in the delaminated region, numerical calculations are conducted by finite element analysis. In order to compromise a real complicated geometry and a finite element mesh for calculation, a simplified model is proposed and referred as an assembled fan model. Correlation of predicted initial buckling stress and mode with experimental results is one of the major points of interest in the present paper.

CAI METHODS AND SPECIMENS

Two types of testing methods are used here as stated, NASA and SACMA. For NASA method, a quasi-isotropic 127×254 mm plate of $\{(45/0/-45/90)_6\}_{sym}$ with 48 ply stacking sequence is cut out of a source plate of both kinds of CFRP. Some specimens with another length of 210mm are also prepared in order to examine the effect of the length upon CAI strength. As the CF/Epoxy material, AS/410 resin system of Mitsubishi Rayon Co. is employed here. This resin system is rather conventional and similar to NARMCO 5208, previous US standard resin. Chosen CF/PEEK material system here is AS4/APC-2. Averaged thickness of the plates is 7.3mm for CF/Epoxy and 6.2mm for CF/PEEK, respectively. This CF/PEEK system is fabricated under recommended procedure³ by ICI Co., particularly in terms of a cooling rate more than $30^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. A thickness difference is caused by a high pressure for CF/PEEK during its processing. For SACMA method, a similar quasi-isotropic 102×152 mm plate of $\{(45/0/-45/90)_4\}_{sym}$ with 32 ply is used. Only CF/Epoxy plates are prepared for this method.

IMPACT TESTS AND DELAMINATION VISUALIZATION

Impact procedure comprises one of very important elements of the CAI test and many complicated parameters possibly affect a mechanism of delamination. However, the least interest is casted upon impact itself. Impact is merely considered as a mean for giving an intended delamination. Therefore, detailed parameters in the impact are basically fixed except for NASA A-11 to A-15 and SACMA D-11 to D-15 specimens. Used machine is a drop-weight type impactor, Dynatup GRC-8250 system. Impact energy level is fixed to approximately 27 Joule for the NASA method excluding the above exceptions, about 3.5kJ/m for CF/Epoxy and 4.3kJ/m for CF/PEEK in normalized expression by a thickness at an impact location. There is one deviation here from the exact NASA definition of the test procedure. The impact is given to the already trimmed plate here for avoiding complication. A picture frame support is designed and used for impact where an open window is $102\text{mm} \times 102\text{mm}$. In the SACMA method, the defined procedure is traced exactly. Several energy levels of impact are given to the smaller plates with the specified frame support. A projectile with a hemisphere top of 12.7mm diameter containing a load cell is used for both methods. Assigned total weight of a projectile-extender-adjust mass system is 5.8 kg. Impact energy level is simply defined by a product of the weight and the drop height.

Figure 1 Fine C-Scope of Impact Delamination

Delamination pattern visualization is conducted by two types of ultrasonic NDI machines, rather conventional Cannon M-500 C-scanner system and highly advanced Krautkraemmer robotic scanning system. Pulse-echo method is mainly used here because information about delamination depth is available through this method. Time of (beam) flight (TOF) C-scope can be converted into delamination depth view through the transverse sound velocity in CFRP laminates. Converted TOF C-scope of impact delamination into depth by the latter system is shown in Fig.1 for a CF/Epoxy plate of NASA method. A spatial geometry of multiple

delamination surface is easily understood. It looks like aperture vanes in lens. The detailed structure of multiple delaminations by impact can be summarized and illustrated as in Fig.2. Thick curves in this figure indicate delamination edge contours in each ply. The first 45° ply delamination looks like a curve drawing template. Diameter growth from the first 45° to the second 45° ply delaminations, which occurs at the 4th-5th ply interface in the global sense, is a very clear feature and it can be imagined from B-scope information. There exists a 4-ply increase in the delamination depth in the same directional laminae. For example, a small imaginary sectional view indicated in the lower center of Fig.2 explains that a delamination at the first 90° ply appears underneath bonded 45/0/-45/90 = 4 plies. Such a clarification of the delamination pattern gives a basis of a mathematical modelling stated later.

Figure 2 Schematic Structure of Impact Delamination

COMPRESSION TESTS AND DISCUSSIONS RELATED WITH CAI VALUES

Compression tests are conducted by an Instron 1128 screw-driven testing machine for the plates after or before impact. Crosshead speed is fixed to 0.2mm/min throughout all the tests. The loading end and side edge fixtures are designed and made after Ref.1 for NASA tests. Commercially available MTS fixtures are used for SACMA tests. In both methods, the loaded and supported ends are considered to be almost clamped and the side edges to be almost simply supported. Basically, 12 strain gages are utilized for recording stress-strain behavior into a computer driven data logger under 0.2 second sampling rate. Figure 3 depicts the behavior of compressive stress vs. the central deflection in the impact side for typical CF/Epoxy and CF/PEEK specimens after impact. For CF/Epoxy, it is clearly shown in Fig.3 that the measured buckling deflection (plate ID.:A-1) is being reversed just before the final collapse type of failure. This phenomenon seems to be quasi-static and occurs without any exception in other impacted NASA type CF/Epoxy specimens. In CF/PEEK specimens after impact, however, such a quasi-static deflection reverse can not be recorded well, while the final failure mode implies that it must happen. Although buckling deflection in CF/PEEK starts at only a little higher stress level than in CF/Epoxy, its growth rate in CF/PEEK is much smaller. Thus, there can be found a great improvement in CF/PEEK CAI strengths as well-known.

Figure 3 Stress-Central Deflection Curves at NASA-CAI Tests

Consecutive Moire-topography pictures for CF/Epoxy are taken from the other side of the impact to clarify the mechanism of the process to the final failure. Demonstration of the pictures are left to the authors' previous publication⁴. Some essential findings are again described here. For CF/Epoxy, the buckling deformation induces a transverse propagation of the delamination to the loading direction. The horizontally penetrated delamination reduces severely a load-bearing capacity of the plate. The timing of complete delamination penetration roughly coincides with the onset of buckling deflection reverse as shown in Fig.3. Consecutive Moire pictures for CF/PEEK reveal that the delamination penetration is well arrested before the instance of final catastrophic failure at much higher stress.

Relationships between CAI strains and normalized impact energy by the thickness are plotted in Fig.4 as a conclusion of this section. In Fig.4, small symbols denote the single data point. It can be understood that CAI strength of CF/PEEK is almost twice of that of conventional CF/Epoxy. A slight dependency of CAI strengths upon applied impact energy is observed. Solid and dashed lines in Fig.4 correspond respectively to CF/PEEK and CF/Epoxy results in Ref.3 by SACMA method. The present SACMA specimens also lead to a little higher results. Although the specimen quantity is not enough for definite conclusion, it should be noted that SACMA methods may provide non-conservative CAI values.

Figure 4 Summary of CAI Strain vs. Normalized Impact Energy

NUMERICAL PREDICTION OF INITIAL BUCKLING BEHAVIOR IN CAI TESTS

Some amount of the preceding work is already done for the prediction of delamination buckling behavior. In the cases of one-dimensional delamination, even in single or multiple, References 5 and 6 give a basic idea and details of the analysis. Reference 6 predicts relatively well the experimental delamination buckling behavior up to a nonlinear state. However, there exist an intrinsic difficulty in such one-dimensional analysis to explain real two-dimensional CAI behavior. Thus, a few papers^{7,8} treat the problem early based on an elliptical modelling. Newly published work such as Refs. 9, 10, 11, and 12 provides some improvement of the original idea. However, there can be found a discrepancy among those papers in the basic analysis philosophy. In Refs. 7, 8, and 12 delaminated region is simplified as an ellipse of a single ply lamina and their target seems to obtain also a physical insight of delamination propagation. According to the authors' trial of direct application of single ply delamination modelling^{7,8} to initial buckling prediction, however, it does provide seriously discrepant result from experimental values. This finding leads to an incentive for the present calculation. Consideration of multiple delamination by impact is rather pursued as realistic as possible in Refs. 9 and 10. Unfortunately, the problem becomes very complicated in this approach particularly in postbuckling range. A drastic simplification is done in Refs. 9 and 11 for the prediction of postbuckling range. A huge nonlinear numerical calculations is done in Ref.10 even without an effect of delamination propagation.

Figure 5 Proposed Assembled Fan Model

The present paper is supposed to stand in-between these two directions. Mathematical modelling is basically conducted upon the understanding of delamination geometry illustrated in Fig.2. The numerical analysis is confined to the prediction of initial buckling behavior. A straightforward finite element modelling of the realistic delamination as Fig.2 requires tens of thousands of elements and analysis efficiency seems to be bad. Hence, a compromised model shown in Fig.5 is proposed here and referred to as an assembled-fan model. This model consists of pairs of opposite octant fans in which stacking sequence is different from each other as indicated in Fig.5. The effects of matrix cracks along the edge of generator strips in each

lamina caused by impact are ignored because the predominant load is compression. A commercial software package, NISA-II, is used for calculation where the isoparametric composite laminate shell element of 4 nodes is chosen. Number of degrees of freedom (DOF) is 2146. Each delaminated octant has different thickness depending on its ply number. It should be noted that multiple layer regions show the bending-extensional coupling effect and that it is automatically considered in finite element analysis (FEA).

Analysis procedure is similar to Refs. 7 and 8 and explained in Fig.6. Uniform strain state in uniaxial compression is assumed in the infinite plate of a quasi-isotropic laminate with Poisson's ratio ν . So, $-\epsilon_x$ and $\nu\epsilon_x$ are induced. Thus, in-plane displacement u and v along the boundary circle of the model of radius a can be easily written as follows:

$$u = -a \epsilon_x \cos \theta, \quad v = a \nu \epsilon_x \sin \theta$$

These displacements are shared with the infinite quasi-isotropic substrate, and hence, an in-plane static problem is solved first under the specified displacement condition and reaction forces at the peripheral nodes are obtained. Then, buckling analysis is conducted using these forces. Boundary conditions in the out-of-plane displacement w along the circle are clamped sets, $w = 0$ and $\partial w / \partial r = 0$. Such conditions are schematically illustrated in Fig.11. Used elastic moduli of CF/Epoxy are; $E_L = 131.0\text{GPa}$, $E_T = 13.0\text{ Gpa}$, $\nu_L = 0.34$, and $G_{LT} = 6.4\text{GPa}$. Although these inputs may be a little larger than true values of AS/410, they are employed here because they seem to be very common in US literature. Special care is required for this point in later discussion with experimental results.

Figure 6 Boundary Conditions

Check calculations are conducted first for comparison with the results of Shivakumar and Whitcomb⁷. The present model coincides with their one if the whole delaminated region is assumed to be a single unidirectional ply. Obtained buckling strains for $a = b = 25.4\text{mm}$, $h = 0.51\text{mm}$ and various off-axis angle α cases agree very well with their FEA predictions (Fig.6 in Ref.7). Thus, the present procedure is justified at least for uniform delamination. Numerical results for the in-plane stress distribution under prescribed displacements are given first in Fig.7. Assumed uniform strain ϵ_x is $0.01\% = 100 \times 10^{-6}$ and diameter is 30mm from now on. This prediction would be compared to the experimental stress results by infrared stress analyzer. For later comparison, Fig.7 is arranged so that the macroscopic loading direction coincides with the vertical axis. The actual calculation is done according to the definition in Fig.10. Transverse stress distribution to the fiber direction in the surface 45° layer is given for such a purpose. It is clearly understood that high transverse stress appears in the octant regions of single layer delamination, i.e., in thin regions. Note that we must not concentrate the discussion of stress state in the vicinity of the center because the center point is a kind of singular point in the rigorous sense and because the assembled fan model does not reflect a flyfot type pattern of a real delamination.

Results of initial buckling analysis are given in the contour plot of out-of-plane displacement from Figure 7 Example of Calculated Stress (σ_T) Distribution at Surface 45 Layer

Figure 8 Buckling Mode (1st) in Delaminated Area [Anti-Symmetric]

Figure 9 Buckling Mode (2nd) in Delaminated Area [Symmetric, Twin Peak]

Fig.8 to Fig.10 for 3 lower eigenvalues. Each eigenvalue λ is indicated in figures and 0.01% strain multiplied by λ means the corresponding buckling strain to each mode. Figure 8 depicts an anti-symmetrical mode and Figures 9 and 10 do symmetrical modes in terms of the neutral surface of the plate. Three λ values are rather close to each other and the next lowest is far from them. Eigenvalue for a single layer circular delamination model is calculated as 2.3384 under the same input data, which is quite different from the those of the assembled fan model stated in the next section.

Figure 10 Buckling Mode (2nd) in Delaminated Area [Symmetric, Single Peak]

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS RELATED TO NUMERICAL BUCKLING PREDICTION AND DISCUSSIONS

Experimentally obtained stress - strain and deflection relations are discussed first with predicted buckling strain. Figure 11 shows typical such relations for CF/Epoxy of the NASA type with an approximately 33mm diameter of inner delamination where the deflection pick-up is placed. Using the central deflection curve equivalent to the curve in Fig.3 and δ^2 plot technique, a buckling stress is determined first as 69.9 MPa in this case. Then experimental buckling strain apart from the delaminated area is obtained as 0.132%. Take a note that this is not a real far field strain. Upon this almost linear stress-strain curve, predicted buckling strains in the previous section are plotted. They are rather close to the experimental value although the single layer

Figure 11 Comparison of Experimental and Analytical Buckling Strain in NASA Plate of CF/Epoxy [Delamination Diameter: 33mm]

delamination solution provides a quite low prediction. If we assume a uniform 4ply disc of 45/0/-45/90, buckling strain becomes 0.188% which is considerably larger than the experiment. Assembled fan results fall between two extreme cases, 0.094%, 0.103% and 0.125%. Thus, the present model provides a considerable improvement in the initial buckling prediction. Note that even higher elastic moduli than reality lead to a lower prediction than the experimental value. The reason is presumably ascribed to a deviation between the model and the exact delamination geometry. A diameter in the initial 45 ply delamination is much smaller than the others as Fig.2. This part of the discussion will be remained for future work.

Concerning admissible buckling mode, only some qualitative implications are obtained so far. Moire pictures taken for some NASA plates indicate that #3 mode in Fig.10 is the most probable case. However, recent experiments for CF/Epoxy SACMA plates with smaller delamination diameters reveal that the twin peak second mode in Fig.9 can also exist. A picture of delaminated portion is shown in Fig.12 where a delamination diameter is roughly 25mm. To the knowledge and experience of the authors, the anti-symmetric mode like Fig.8 is not encountered. A most conservative conclusion is that the assembled fan model provides closer predictions to the experiment than the single and uniform delamination model both in terms of mode and buckling strain.

Figure 12 Captured Twin Peak Mode in Buckling for CF/Epoxy

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS RELATED TO STRESS DISTRIBUTION AND DISCUSSIONS

A supporting experimental evidence of the assembled fan model is obtained through a very modern device, an infrared stress graphic system (ISGS). A principle of this system is a thermo-elastic effect of solids, i.e., temperature of a solid is going down and up corresponding to tension and compression in an adiabatic state. Thus, temperature fluctuation amplitude δT can be converted into stress amplitude in cyclic loading conditions if we have very accurate and quick thermography camera and a device for synchronizing load and temperature fluctuation. A schematic illustration of measurement is given in Fig.13. An effect of temperature change with an off-frequency from the load is removed like this figure. In the case of carbon fiber composites, δT can be related almost to $\delta\sigma_T$, transverse stress to the fiber in the top surface layer as explained in Ref.13. The system used here is JTG-8000 by Nippon Denshi Co. LTD. Because cyclic loading is mandatory, a hydraulic machine is preferable rather than a screw driven machine. Loading level is limited to approximately a half of the buckling stress of delaminated area. Although the measurements are conducted for both sides of impact, the reverse side of impact does not provide better results probably because of seriously opening matrix cracks which prohibit compression load transfer in the surface delaminated layer. In the impact side, the matrix cracks by impact

Figure 13 Schema in Infra Red Stress Measurement

Figure 14 Measured Temperature Amplitude Corresponding to σ_T in top 45° ply for SACMA CF/Epoxy

are in a micro scale and can carry in-plane compressive loads as assumed. Measured temperature amplitude distribution in the impact side for one of SACMA specimens of CF/Epoxy is shown in Fig.14 where indication of delamination is not fully clear partly because of low S/N ratio due to the limited load amplitude. However, it can be identified here that the temperature amplitude on the surface of thin regions appears to be greater than on thick regions. Qualitative trend coincides with the numerical stress distribution shown in Fig.7. This finding supports the assembled fan modelling.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Experimental investigation is conducted for understanding unveiled CAI behavior of thick plates of CF/PEEK and CF/Epoxy. The process of delamination propagation in the final phase of CF/Epoxy CAI tests is well understood particularly for NASA method. Due to an ability of delamination arresting, CAI strain of CF/PEEK thick plates becomes almost twice of that of CF/Epoxy. For compromising simplicity and reality, the assembled fan model is proposed where the stacking sequence of each octant of a circular delamination area is idealized based on an ultrasonic visualization image of the real impact damage. A pretty much improved prediction of macroscopic initial buckling strain can be obtained by this model. Experimental results suggest that two kinds of symmetric modes with respect to the neutral surface, single and twin peak modes, are definitely observed. It should be noted that the twin peak mode can never be obtained by the uniform layer delamination. A direct stress measurement device, ISGS, provides a supporting experimental fact, qualitatively similar transverse stress distribution around the impact point to numerical prediction by the assembled fan model. The geometry of the real delamination in which the thickness of delaminated region depends on the orientation and distance from the impact point plays a primary role of such a stress distribution.

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